

ASSESSING INCOME GENERATION ACTIVITIES IN WEST AND CENTRAL DARFUR STATES

Dr. Badreldin Mohamed Ahmed Abdulrahman ¹, Dr. Tarig Ibrahim Mohamed Abdelmalik ²

¹Department of Economics, Faculty of Economics and Social Studies, University of Zalingei

²Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zalingei

*Correspondence Author: badreco@gmail.com

Abstract:

Income defines as the money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service or through investing capital and it is consume to fuel day to day expenditure. This study has been conducted in 2014. The objective of this study is to assess income generation activities in Darfur, particularly in Geneina and Zalingei localities of West and Central Darfur (WCD) by using questionnaire its size 80 individuals, we obtained the following results a. Agriculture is the main and alternative source of income in WCD b. Financing is the main problem in WCD c. The role of National and local government and united nations (UN) agencies in generating income is less than that played by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international non-governmental organizations (INGOs).

Keywords:

Income, Generation, Agriculture, Activities, WC Darfur.

Cite This Article: Dr. Badreldin Mohamed Ahmed Abdulrahman, and Dr. Tarig Ibrahim Mohamed Abdelmalik, “Assessing Income Generation Activities in West And Central Darfur States.” *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah*, Vol. 3, No. 1(2015): 19-25.

1. INTRODUCTION

Income generation is defining as interventions attempt to address poverty, unemployment, and lack of economic opportunities to increase participant's ability to generate income and secure livelihood. The interventions can take a wide variety of forms, including microcredit programs that provide small loans to individuals or groups, who would not normally qualify for loans from conventional financial institutions. Microcredit is one form of microfinance, which involves the provision of a wider range of financial services, such as access to savings, credit, and insurance to poor people. In addition to microcredit, other income generation interventions focus on business and vocational skills training for participants, either for positions within existing industries or to develop small businesses of their own. Both microcredit and vocational skills training programs may include additional components not related to income generation, such as health, education, women's empowerment, critical thinking, and communication skills. Many also have strong social support components (Research to Prevention, 2013).

The objective of this study is to assess income generation activities in Darfur, particularly in Geneina and Zalingei localities of West and Central Darfur by using questionnaire its size 80 individuals. This paper includes five sections, section two reviews literature, section three overviews income generation activities in Darfur. Findings, results and conclusion remarks are given in section four and five respectively.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Most individuals gain income through earning wages by working and/ or making investments into financial assets like stocks, bonds and real estate. In most countries earned income is taxed by the government before it is received. The revenue generated by income taxes finances government actions and programs as determined by federal and state budgets (Investopedia, 2014).

Many development agencies are increasing their emphasis on assisting women to secure income through their own efforts. Such approaches are often categorized as 'income-generating activities' and cover initiatives as diverse as small business promotion, cooperative undertakings, job creation schemes, sewing circles, credit and savings groups and youth training programs. So, how can 'income-generation' are defined? It is sometimes argued that education and health provision, legal and political changes, and global economics all affect the abilities of people to secure an income. From this stems the confusion in the use of the term 'income-generation'. For the purpose of this paper, 'income-generating activities' will be considered those initiatives that affect the economic aspects of people's lives through the use of economic tools such as credit. Other types of support affecting women's production are considered complementary to income-generating activities. For example, these might include child care or basic services provision and labor-saving technologies (www.gdrc.org).

Because conflicts tend to have a very negative impact on the economy of a country/region, the economic situation in both displacement-producing and neighboring recipient areas is in many cases relatively poor as well. Displacement frequently results in the loss of key livelihood assets, such as land, production materials, infrastructure or financial capital. Without access to their regular asset base, including the means for income generation, refugees and IDPs become dependent on the passive reception of relief aid and support from the host community. In such a situation, income generation is a key programmatic strategy to address the need to find alternative means to make a living in a dignified way: it aims at creating opportunities for the use of resources among displaced people in a meaningful way and with the objective of becoming less dependent, more self-reliant and able to care for the family. Furthermore, providing support to income generation activities among people of concern, including host communities, can support local economic development in a broader sense: income generation programs frequently provide new skills, services and opportunities for host communities and can stimulate the local economy, thereby linking relief with development. Similarly, this is the case when displaced people avail themselves of a durable solution (Danish Refugees council, 2013).

DRC defines *income generating activities* as ‘small-scale projects that create an income source to individual beneficiaries or beneficiary groups whilst promoting a) the principal right to self-determination and b) the objectives of integration, repatriation and (re-)integration’. DRC uses the notion of income generation relatively broadly and as a cover term for a wide variety of activities such as micro-credit, grants, skills- and vocational training, business training, cash/food for work (asset creation) schemes, local economic development initiatives and even small- and medium enterprise development.

There are three ways through which income can be generated. Firstly, income generation does not always mean the immediate getting of money, although in the end we use money to place a measurable value on the goods and services people produce. An example of income generation which does not lead to getting money would be a situation where a productive person produces enough food to feed him or her and the family. Skills have been used to meet immediate needs and thus savings have been achieved. A money value can be placed on the food produced and so the food can be seen as income (Rex and Subbarao, 1993). A second way a person can generate income is by astute investment of existing resources. An example would be development of a piece of land through planting a crop for sale. The money gained is income. An indirect form of investment is to bank savings or to purchase part ownership (shares) in a productive enterprise such as a business (Money generated from such investments is income). A third way to generate income is for people to use their skills by serving another person who pays for the use of those skills. That is the yearn wages.

3. INCOME GENERATION ACTIVITIES IN DARFUR

The Darfur region is amongst one of the most important regions in the Republic of Sudan. Its natural resource wealth - fertile soil, geographic location, and climate - makes it of utmost importance for the prosperity of the Sudanese economy. The region occupies around half a million acres, roughly 20% of Sudan, and holds abundant mineral and livestock resources. The climate of the region allows agriculture to depend entirely on rain. Both agriculture and livestock are the two main pillars of the region’s economic foundation. Animal livestock contributed to 50% of Sudan’s balance of payments between 1976 and 1984, 20% of National Domestic Product, and 25% of the country’s total animal livestock. Moreover, the region produces several kinds of agricultural crops, fruits, and seeds. Also, different minerals such as copper, uranium, and oil could be found in abundant amounts throughout the region. Economic research confirms Darfur’s capability of sustaining a population of 300 million, while providing adequate food supply. However, research suggests that this could only be valid if Darfur’s political climate becomes stable; only then the region could prosper (www.Africaecon.org).

The state of West Darfur¹ in the far west of Sudan in the longitudinal international border of about 750 km with both Chad and the Central African Republic is one of the major states of Darfur,

¹ The West Darfur divided into two states in 2011. So the term West Darfur here includes West and Central Darfur States

which have been affected by events experienced over the past seven years, which has had a significant impact on all aspects of life.

According to the national Census in 2008, West Darfur State has a total population of 1,292,714 people, with an annual growth rate of 3.4%. These individuals live on a surface of area about 75000 km^2 , giving an average density 17.4 persons per km^2 . However, people are spread very unevenly across the state, with large areas uninhabited and many other areas very sparsely populated. Sadly, the whole picture of population is extremely disturbed since conflicts took place in Darfur in 2003. Thousands of people displaced from their homes, either internally or to the neighboring countries, with most of them live in refugee camps. Nomads could cross the borders to west Darfur from Chad and Republic of Central Africa and vice versa. This in turn makes the number of population unstable for accurate registering in some areas like (Jebal Moon, Jebal Marrah... etc)

- Population: 1,292,714
- Localities: 15
- Administration Units: 46
- Villages: 1244
- Special Groups: IDPs, Refugees, Nomads

Darfurians lives in there villages' - this axiom is as true today as it was when the country became independent 60 years ago. Over 90.00 per cent of the population lives in rural areas. Agriculture and related activities in rural Darfur contribute to 20.00 per cent of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and is responsible for the employment of over 60.00 per cent of the workforce. Hence, when one talks of socio-economic progress in India, what is mostly? Relevant is how the lives of the rural people have changed.

Some of Darfur's poorest hides and skins producers are getting a chance to benefit from the growing regional demand of leather products with UNDP's pilot project (Darfur Livelihoods Value Chain Project) working to improve production techniques for leather production in Sudan. The tannery and leather production has been referred to as one of the main windows of livelihood opportunities in Darfur. Its advantage lies in its potential of being a valuable source of income for a large sector women and men across Darfur. In West Darfur alone, where the industry is likely to witness a new business boom, the Hides and Skin Value Chain project helps around 1,000 leather producers (UNDP, 2013).

4. METODOLOGY, DATA COLLECTION AND FINDINGS

The study adopted descriptive analytical methods. Data of the study were obtained by using questionnaire its size 80 individuals from Central and West Darfur.

By using questionnaire for 80 individuals (33) male and (47) female, we found that (50) of respondent are marriage and (12) are single and (18) are widow and divorce. The following tables show the answers of individuals:

Table 1: Educational levels of respondents

Educational Level	Frequencies	Percentage %
University	10	0.13
Secondary School	8	0.10
Primary School	16	0.20
Khalwa	10	0.13
Illiterate	36	0.44

Source: own calculated

From above table we observe that only 13% of respondent are graduates compare with 44% are illiterate. This means that this community faced the problem of illiterate.

Table 2: Main Source of Income

Source	Frequencies	Percentage %
Agriculture	24	0.30
Pastoral	4	0.05
Agro- Pastoral	4	0.05
Commercial	17	0.21
Other	31	0.39

Source: own calculated

From table (2) we report that the main source of income in WCD (West and Central Darfur) is Agriculture and the second one is commercial.

Table 3: Alternative Source of Income

Source	Percentage %
Agriculture	0.30
Building	0.18
Commercial	0.23
Tea Making	0.15
Other	0.14

Source: own calculated

Table (3) reports that agriculture also form alternative source of income for those who work in other jobs.

Table 4: is the main source of income give surplus time for other activities

Answer	Percentage %
yes	0.26
No	0.43
To some extend	0.31

Source: own calculated

Table 5: what is the role played by the following in generating income for poor people?

Institute	Adequate role%	Neutral%	Inadequate%
National government	0.43	0.10	0.47
Local government	0.27	0.27	0.46
NGOs	0.42	0.15	0.43
INGOs	0.51	0.24	0.25
UN agencies	0.31	0.34	0.35

Source: own calculation

From above table we observe the following:

- The INGOs play adequate role comparing with other institutes (about 51% of respondent assured that the role of INGOs is adequate).
- About 31% of respondent say that UN agencies play adequate role.
- About 42%, 27% and 43% answered that NGOs, local government and National government play adequate role in generating income.

5. CONCLUSION REMARKS

This study is an attempt to assessing income generating activities in WCD. We adopted descriptive analytical method and used questionnaire its size 80 individuals. After analyzing we obtained the following results:

- Agriculture is the main and alternative source of income in WCD.
- Financing is the main problem in WCD.
- The role of National and local government and UN agencies in generating income is less than that played by NGOs and INGOs.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Danish Refugees council Report, 2013
[2] Hall, S e tal (Undated). *Assessing Income Generation Activities in Zare and Kishindih: Survey commissioned by PIN (people in need). Paris, France.*

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of RESEARCH –GRANTHAALAYAH

A knowledge Repository

-
- [3] R&P (Undated). *A report on Research Prevention: Income Generation, Rigorous Evidence – Usable Results.*
- [4] *United Nation Development Program (UNDP), 2013.*
- [5] www.Africaecon.org.
- [6] www.investopedia.com.